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BIOCATALYTIC STRATEGIES FOR THE DEGRADATION OF EMERGING MICROPOLLUTANTS: FROM NANOPLASTICS TO PHARMACEUTICALS

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Abstract

In recent decades, the increasing occurrence of micropollutants, including nanoplastics, microplastics, pesticides, hydrocarbons, chlorinated solvents, and pharmaceuticals, among others, has raised growing concern. Innovative enzymatic systems targeting nanoplastic degradation have been reported and are under active development, though extending these approaches to plastics beyond PET remains a significant challenge. In the case of pharmaceuticals, the biodegradation of some compounds is possible; however, for others, the degradation pathways remain unresolved. In this work, we focus on some such pharmaceuticals: paracetamol, enalapril, ibuprofen, and atenolol micropollutants that have attracted significant attention due to their widespread use as an antipyretic and analgesic, and their potential to be released into surface waters, groundwater, wastewater and seawater at concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 200 µg/L. Microorganisms with a strong natural capacity to degrade for example paracetamol, often characterized by diverse metabolic capabilities and unique physiological traits, can be exploited as natural biocatalysts in wastewater treatment, while their degradation mechanisms can also be elucidated.

In this work, we present results on the efficacy of novel natural and engineered biologics for the degradation of two types of micropollutants: nanoplastics/microplastics and the aforementioned pharmaceuticals. For the latter, we provide evidence of the degradation capacity of bacteria from the genera *Alcanivorax*, *Paraburkholderia*, and *Pseudomonas*. We also describe an alginate-based bacterial immobilization process that enables complete paracetamol degradation, enhances cell stability and reusability, and reduces downstream processing costs[5].

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Keywords

Bioremediation • pharmaceuticals • Micropollutants • Biocatalysis